

Studies on stability of biuret based polyurethane potting compound under autoclaving conditions

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Studies on the stability of biuret based polyurethane potting compound under autoclaving conditions have been carried out. Polyurethane potting compound prepared with castor oil and biuret of dicyclohexyl methane diisocyanate (H₁₂-MDI) has appreciable dimensional stability. Degradation is noticed after initial autoclaving. However, crosslinking is noticed after repeated autoclaving providing stability to the present potting compound.

Polyurethanes are widely recognized as the most biocompatible and haemocompatible polymers utilized in the medical devices industry¹. Degradation during processing and long-term implantation has been noticed with aromatic polyurethanes².

Gamma radiation and autoclaving are used to sterilize the biomedical devices. Excessive and repeated sterilization cause chain scission of polyurethane and formation of low molecular weight components². A potential carcinogenic chemical 4,4'-methylenedianiline (MDA) is formed in thermoplastic 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI) based polyurethane during autoclaving sterilization. The resistance of aromatic diisocyanates (TDI, MDI etc.)-based polyurethanes to thermohydrolytic degradation is poor in comparison with that of polyurethanes based on aliphatic polyurethanes². For this reason polyurethanes based on dicyclohexyl methane diisocyanate (H₁₂-MDI) have been developed for various biomedical applications³. Adhesives and potting compounds based on aliphatic polyurethanes lead to surface modification of PVC materials⁴ and potting of hollow fiber bundles in dialyzer housing components for the development of haemodialyzers⁴. Stability of the potting compound to sterilization conditions is a concern for the development of haemodialyzer. The present paper deals with the studies on the effect of a multifunctional isocyanate (biuret) and castor oil monomers on the stability of polyurethane under autoclave sterilization.

Results and Discussion

The setting time of the hydroxy-terminated polyurethane prepolymer (Component A) with the biuret of H₁₂-MDI (Component B) is given in Table 1. Taken together, higher the isocyanate index of components A and

'B', lower is the setting time. The formulation, SD/02(0.44)/2.8, offers the lowest setting time (10 min). Therefore, this formulation was selected as candidate potting compound for further evaluation of autoclaving-induced degradation.

Table 1. Setting time of potting compounds of hydroxy-terminated polyurethane prepolymer with biuret of H₁₂-MDI

Sl. no.	Component A prepolymer (NCO/OH ratio)	Component B	NCO/OH ratio of Comp A+B	Setting time min
1.	SD/02 (0.44)	Biuret of H ₁₂ -MDI	1.5	15
2.	SD/02 (0.44)	Biuret of H ₁₂ -MDI	2.0	12
3.	SD/02 (0.44)	Biuret of H ₁₂ -MDI	2.80	10

The cured potting material, SD/02(0.44)/2.8 undergoes no change in dimension during the thermal aging at 70°. However, the weight loss is 2.94%. The change of weight with time plot reveals that the initial weight-loss is due to loss of residual solvent remaining after curing or due to the loss of isopropanol liberated during decapping of the capped-biuret of H₁₂-MDI (Component 'B'). It also shows that there is no weight-loss after 30 days at 70°.

The stability of the cured potting material in repeated cycles of autoclaving was assessed from the UV spectral analysis of the extract of the autoclaved sample. The UV spectrum of the extract of the autoclaved sample (4 cycle) shows a major peak at 208 nm with minor peaks at 226 and 272 nm indicating degradation. These peaks are different from that of 246 nm observed for the hydroxy-terminated polyurethane prepolymer (Component, A), SD/02(0.44). The UV spectrum of the methanol extract of the unautoclaved cured sample (control) also reveals a peak at 226 nm. The data on the UV analysis on the extent of degradation and leaching of low molecular weight fractions

from the cured material was calculated based on the absorbance at 226 nm and are presented in Table 2. The absorbance at 226 nm observed for the control sample (unautoclaved) indicates the possibility of chemical attack of polyurethane by methanol itself during the extraction. It has been reported elsewhere that the boiling methanol induces degradation in urethane and allophanate linkages producing low molecular weight polyurethanes.⁵ Bruck⁵ also reported that boiling methanol degrades the polyurethane polymer at the urethane linkage to give low molecular weight polyurethanes which are subsequently extracted from the polymer. Ratner⁵ also reported that methanol-acetone extraction degrades the polymer at the urethane linkage

Table 2 Absorbance of methanol extract from 1 g of the cured potting compound (SD/02 (0.44)/2.8) after autoclave sterilization

Sample	Number of cycles of autoclaving	Calculated total absorbance for methanol soluble fraction at ~226 nm	Effective absorbance for autoclave sterilization
SD/02 (0.44)/2.8 0	No autoclaving (Control)	157	-
SD/02 (0.44)/2.8 1	1	200	43
SD/02 (0.44)/2.8 2	2	189	32
SD/02 (0.44)/2.8 3	3	68.5	-
SD/02 (0.44)/2.8 4	4	184	27

Though the resistance of the polyurethanes based on aliphatic diisocyanates to thermohydrolytic degradation is better in comparison with that of polyurethanes based on aromatic diisocyanates (TDI, MDI etc),² the earlier investigation revealed that aliphatic polyurethanes based on H₁₂-MDI, castor oil and 1,2-propanediol undergo hydrolytic degradation.⁶ However, the aliphatic polyurethanes based on H₁₂-MDI, castor oil and 1,6-hexamethylenediamine are fairly stable against hydrolytic and oxidative degradation which is attributed to the presence of urea linkages in the hard segment.⁶ The urea linkages in the hard segment can form virtual crosslinks and act as shield to prevent degradation at the ester and urethane linkages. Therefore, the crosslinks (physical as well as chemical) present in these polyurethanes could provide resistance to degradation to a greater extent. The present cured potting compound is a chemically crosslinked product. However, the UV analysis suggests that the autoclaving induces degradation. This is attributed to the thermohydrolytic degradation at ester linkages of castor oil units and weakening the matrix initially and then to the thermohydrolytic degradation at the urethane linkages of the polyurethane. The thermohydrolytic degradation at the urethane linkages of the polyurethane is presented in Scheme 1.

The autoclaving and methanol treatment produce similar low molecular weight compounds from the cured potting material. Therefore, the effective degradation due to the autoclaving-induced degradation is that deduced from the total degradation. Therefore, the effective absorbance

for autoclaving-induced degradation is the total calculated absorbance minus the absorbance for the methanol-induced degradation (Table 2).

Scheme 1 Thermohydrolytic degradation and crosslinking

The data on the first cycle of autoclaving reveal enhanced degradation of polyurethane potting compound as evidenced from the increased absorbance. After the second cycle of autoclaving, leaching is found to be decreased which may be due to the onset of secondary reactions, forming allophanate linkage in the degraded polyurethane as shown in Scheme 1. The formation of allophanate linkage in the radiation-sterilized sample of the potting compound has been reported elsewhere.⁷ During the third cycle, the effective autoclaving-induced degradation is insignificant. Further increase on the cycles of autoclaving induces autoclaving-induced degradation. This is presumably due to the degradation of allophanate linkage.

From these observations, it can be concluded that initial autoclaving of cured polyurethane potting material based on castor oil and biuret of H₁₂-MDI induces degradation and leaching of low molecular weight fragments. However, the effective autoclaving-induced degradation is reduced significantly after the third cycle. Therefore, the disposable devices developed from this potting compound can be

repeatedly autoclaved before being put in use in such circumstances where the repeated autoclaving is carried before even the first use.

Experimental

Preparation of potting compound : The potting compound consisted of two components, A and B. The polyurethane prepolymer was prepared as component A using castor oil (vacuum-dried) and H₁₂-MDI by solution polymerization using dibutyltin dilaurate catalyst and dimethylacetamide solvent at 140° for a duration of 2.5 h. The mole ratio of H₁₂-MDI and castor oil in the prepolymer preparation was 0.44 : 1.0. The diisocyanate was added dropwise to the castor oil and allowed to react to form a hydroxy-terminated polyurethane prepolymer. The prepolymer was vacuum-dried to remove the solvent. The formation of the prepolymer is presented Scheme 2. The hydroxy-terminated polyurethane prepolymer was coded as SD/02 (0.44). It was analyzed by UV-visible spectrophotometry using a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer. The biuret of

Scheme 2. Formation of component A of potting compound

H₁₂-MDI was prepared as component B using H₁₂-MDI, alcohol and water. H₁₂-MDI and water were reacted using 1 : 3 mole ratio at 140° then cooled and added to isopropanol to get a end-capped isocyanates when a viscous white resin appeared (Component B).

Characterization of potting compound : The setting studies of the hydroxy-terminated polyurethane prepolymer (Component A) was determined using Component B. The setting time was determined as per ASTM Standard F451-76. The prepolymer (2 g) and calculated amount of Component B as per the NCO/OH ratio given in Table 1 were used for the setting studies. Initially the biuret of H₁₂-MDI (Component B) was activated by heating to 190° for 15 min before adding to prepolymer component A. The mixture was cooled to 60° and the setting determined as mentioned above. The setting data of potting Compounds with various isocyanate index with biuret of H₁₂-MDI (Component B) are given in Table 1.

Preparation of cured potting compound : The formulation SD/02(0.44)/2.8 (which offers low setting time) was selected from Table 1 for the preparation of potting com-

pounds. The potting compounds was cured with biuret of H₁₂-MDI (Component B) as mentioned in setting studies. The formation of the crosslinked potting compound is presented in Scheme 3. The dimensional stability was checked with cured potting compounds by keeping at the temperature 70 ± 1° for 2 months as per ASTM D 2126.

Scheme 3 Setting of potting compound

Evaluation of stability under autoclaving conditions : The stability of cured potting compound in autoclaving conditions was investigated by subjecting the sample (1 g) to repeated autoclaving. The autoclaving conditions was 127°, 20 psi and 10 min. The maximum cycles for repeated autoclaving was limited to 4 cycles. The sterilized samples were immersed in methanol (20 ml) and kept at 40° for 30 days. The methanol extract of the sterilized samples was subjected to vacuum evaporation using a rotary evaporator at 60°. The residue was redissolved in methanol using a definite quantity. The methanol solution was used for the analysis of degraded and/or leached low molecular weight compounds from the sterilized samples using the UV-visible spectrophotometer. The stability of cured-potting in harsh chemical treatment of hot methanol was also carried out to identify the effect of methanol on the stability which acted as a control experiment.

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